

Diversity of organic-walled microfossils in the phosphates of the ca. 1 Ga Diabaig Formation, Torridon Group, NW Scotland.

Edwin Rodriguez Dzul, Corentin C. Loron, Heda Agić, Sherri Donaldson, Pamela Knoll, Sean McMahon.

Supplementary Information

- 1) Supplementary Figures
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Supplementary Figure 2. Pie charts with the results of the SHERPA analysis and shape templates used. The pie charts are coloured according to the corresponding templates below. Outlines denote the shapes with a morphological 'tapered' component. Cells of *E. lacustrina* clearly differ from those of *E. moorei* and *Eosynechococcus sp.*, with a higher proportion of tapered shapes.

Supplementary Figure 3. Comparison of *Minimarmilla multicateneria* and extant red algae. (1-7) Characteristic strands with cell-like units of this fossil (as described in main Figure 8) showing similarity with the pericentral cells, thallus apices, cystocarp, and trichoblasts from different modern species of Ceramiales. (8) Terminal cystocarp structure of *Herposiphonia parca* showing an oval shape (Albis-Salas and Galvio, 2011). (9) Another cystocarp example from *Polysiphonia foetidissima* (Diaz-Tapia and Barbara, 2013). (10) Apex of an erected axis of *Bryocladia kanamalukana* with trichoblasts (Diaz-Tapia and Verbruggen, 2023). (11) Erect axis of *Polysiphonia lobophoralis* showing a lateral branch (arrowhead) and a trichoblast in development (arrow) (Mamoozadeh and Freshwater, 2012). (12) Pericentral cells from a squashed erected axis of *Polysiphonia lobophoralis* with pericentral cells and scar cells (arrows) (Mamoozadeh and Freshwater, 2012). (13) Apex of a branch of *Herposiphonia parca* with three terminal trichoblasts (Silva and Fuji, 2012). Scale bars = (10) 100 μm , (1, 4, 7, 9, 11, 12) 50 μm , (2,3, 5, 6) 25 μm , (13) 20 μm , (8) 13 μm .

Supplementary Figure 4. Front and back view of *Minimarmilla* knob-like structure. 1) Front view of thin section. The arrow points to a terminal structure attached to a bundle of filaments. 2) Back view of thin section. The arrow points to the same structure seen from behind; towards the lower right, the usual pattern of cell-like units can be seen (albeit blurrily because the photograph is affected by tens of microns of section). Although the structure could be a small twisted cyanobacterial bundle, it also somewhat resembles a red algal cystocarp.

2) Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Name of Diabaig Formation localities, geographical coordinates, sample labels, and thin sections used in this study.

Locality name	Sample	Thin section	Geological Unit	GPS location
Lower Diabaig	LDR3	LDR3-A	Diabaig Formation	57.577762 N
	LD22-41.2	LDR3-B		-5.688142 E
		LDR3-C		
		LDR3-D		
		LDR3-La		
		LDR3-Lb		
		LD22-41.2		
Badachro	BD22-210	BD22-210-A	Diabaig Formation	57.693072 N
		BD22-210-B1		-5.718739 E
		BD22-210-B2		
Badenscallie	BC-ACH	BC-ACH	Diabaig Formation	58.023233 N
	BC22-SH3	BC-ACH-A		-5.354641 E
	BC22-LO	BC-ACH-B		
		BC22-SH3-A		
		BC22-SH3-B		
		BC22-SH3a		
		BC22-SH3b		
		BC22-SH3c		
		BC22-LO-A		
		BC22-LO-B		
Salmon Farm	SF22-ENP	SF22-ENP	Diabaig Formation	57.531747 N
		SF22-ENPa		-5.612497 E
		SF22-ENPb		
		SF22-ENPc		
		SF22-ENPd		
		SF22-ENPe		
		SF22-ENPf		
		SF22-ENP-X		
		SF22-ENP-Y		
		SF22-ENP-L		
		SF22-ENP-N		
		SF22-ENP-E2		
		SF22-FLO-2		
Road cut above Lower Diabaig	RCA	RCA-1	Diabaig Formation	57.581627 N
		RCA-2		-5.681572 E

Supplementary Table 2. Torridonian OWM compared with other penecontemporaneous Meso-Neoproterozoic assemblages (based on Loron et al., 2019). Fossil and geochronology information from literature and original data are presented. For artificial fossil classes (i.e., *Leiosphaeridia* spp., *Siphonophycus* spp., *Tortunema* spp., *Oscilatoriopsis* spp., *Rugosoopsis* spp.) only the genera were used except for *L. ternata*, *S. punctatum*, and *S. gigas*. Taxa of this study are marked with (*). Am.= assemblage, M.= method, Ref.= reference, Tx.= taxa.

Am.	Lower Shaler Supergroup, Canada	Liulaobei Formation, China	Atar/El Mreiti Group, Mauritania	Lower Madhubani Group, India	Mbuji-Mayi Supergroup, Democratic Republic of Congo	Lower Bylot Supergroup, Canada	Lakhanda Group, Russia	Mirojedikha Formation, Russia	Torridon Group, Scotland	Gouhou Formation, China
Age (M.)	~1232–892 Ma (Re-Os/U-Pb)	~1110–945 Ma (Detrital zircon U-Pb)	1107±37 Ma (Re-Os)	1100–720 Ma (Detrital zircon)	1065–1030 Ma (U-Pb/U-Th-Pb)	~1048–1046 Ma (Re-Os)	1025±40 Ma (Pb-Pb/U-Pb)	~1000–800 Ma (?)	994±48 Ma (Rb-Sr)	890–740 Ma (Detrital zircon U-Pb)
Ref.	Loron et al., 2019, Rayner & Rainbird 2013; Van Acken et al., 2013.	Tang et al., 2013; Li et al., 2021.	Beghin et al., 2017a,b.	Tang et al., 2017; Xiao et al., 2016.	Baludikay et al., 2016; François et al., 2017.	Hofmann & Jackson, 1994; Greenman et al., 2023.	Hermann, 1990; Semikhatov et al., 2000.	Hermann, 1990; Jankauskas et al., 1989.	Turnbull et al., 1996; Strother et al., 2011; Battinson, 2012; Strother & Wellman, 2016; Strother et al., 2021; This study*	Tang et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2023.
Tx.	<i>'Comasphaeridium' tonium</i>	<i>Eotylotopalla grandis</i>	<i>Arctacellularia tetragonala</i>	<i>Annulusia annulata</i>	<i>Arctacellularia tetragonala</i>	<i>Arctacellularia tetragonala</i>	<i>Annulusia annulata</i>	<i>Aimia delicata</i>	<i>Archaeoellipsoides bactrophyucus</i>	<i>Chuarua circularis</i>
	<i>Arctacellularia tetragonala</i>	<i>Fabiformis baffinensis</i>	cf. <i>Coneosphaera</i> sp.	<i>Caudosphaera expansa</i>	cf. <i>Tappania</i> sp.	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis contexta</i>	<i>Caudosphaera expansa</i>	<i>Arctacellularia tetragonala</i>	<i>Archaeoellipsoides conjunctivus</i>	<i>Dictyosphaera tacita</i>
	<i>Caelatimurus foveolatus</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis contexta</i>	<i>Devisphaera corallis</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis kanshiensis</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis kanshiensis</i>	<i>Elatera binata</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis contexta</i>	<i>Archaeoellipsoides grandis</i>	<i>Eosynochococcus moorei</i>
	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis contexta</i>	<i>Myxococcoides ovata</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis kanshiensis</i>	<i>Jacutianema solubila</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis zairensis</i>	<i>Coneosphaera arctica</i>	<i>Elatera unistriata</i>	<i>Coneosphaera</i> sp.	<i>Archaeorestis</i> sp.	<i>Fabiformis baffinensis</i>
	<i>Chuarua circularis</i>	<i>Navifusa majensis</i>	<i>Chlorogloeaopsis zairensis</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Coneosphaera</i> sp.	<i>Coneosphaera</i> sp.	<i>Eosaccoromyces ramosus</i>	<i>Cucunifoma</i> sp.	<i>Bicellum brasieri</i> *	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>
	<i>Coneosphaera</i> sp.	<i>Ostiana microcystis</i>	<i>Chuarua circularis</i>	<i>Navifusa acantimorpha</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis elegans</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis elegans</i>	<i>Eosolena luculosa</i>	<i>Glomovertella einiseica</i>	<i>Eohalotheca lacustrina</i> *	<i>Navifusa majensis</i>
	<i>Culcitulisphaera revelata</i>	<i>Pololeptus rugosus</i>	<i>Comasphaeridium tonium</i>	<i>Polythrichoides lineatus</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis malgica</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis malgica</i>	<i>Flabelleforma compacta</i>	<i>Heliconema turukhania</i>	<i>Germinosphaera bispinosa</i> *	<i>Polythrichoides lineatus</i>
	<i>Daedalosphaera digitisigna</i>	<i>Polythrichoides lineatus</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis irregularis</i>	<i>Simia annulare</i>	<i>Fabiformis baffinensis</i>	<i>Fabiformis baffinensis</i>	<i>Lakhandinia prolata</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia</i> spp.	<i>Globophycus minor</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>
	<i>Dictyosphaera macroreticulata</i>	<i>Simia annulare</i>	<i>Eomicrocystis malgica</i>	<i>Siphonophycus gigas</i>	<i>Germinosphaera bispinosa</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Myxococcoides minor</i>	<i>Gloeodiniopsis lamellosa</i>	<i>Squamosphaera colonialica</i>
	<i>Dictyosphaera tacita</i>	<i>Simia simica</i>	<i>Gemmuloides doncooki</i>	<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>	<i>Glomovertella miroedikha</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>	<i>Navifusa bacillaris</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia</i> spp.*	<i>Symplassiosphaeridium</i> spp.
	<i>Eoschizothrix composita</i>	<i>Siphonophycus gigas</i>	<i>Jacutianema solubila</i>	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Jacutianema solubila</i>	<i>Lophosphaeridium granulatum</i>	<i>Lomentunella vaginata</i>	<i>Obruchevella valdaica</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i> *	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>
	<i>Eosolena</i> sp.	<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia atava</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Navifusa acantimorpha</i>	<i>Majasphaeridium carpogenum</i>	<i>Octoedryxium truncatum</i>	<i>Lophosphaeridium</i> sp.	<i>Tawuia dalensis</i>

<i>Eosynochococcus moorei</i>	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia kulgunica</i>	<i>Tortunema spp.</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>	<i>Navifusa bacillaris</i>	<i>Majasphaeridium sp.</i>	<i>Oscillatorioopsis spp.</i>	<i>Microfossils with reticulate wall</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>
<i>Germinosphaera bispinosa</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>	<i>Lophosphaeridium granulatum</i>	<i>Navifusa majensis</i>	<i>Mucorites ritheicus</i>	<i>Palaeolyngbya hebeiensis</i>	<i>Maculosphaera kingstonensis</i>	<i>Unnamed form</i>
<i>Gigantosphaeridium fibratum</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>	<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera botula</i>	<i>Myxococcoides minor</i>	<i>Nostocomorpha sp.</i>	<i>Mycosphaeroides caudatus</i>	<i>Palaeolyngbya helva</i>	<i>Minimarmilla multicateneria*</i>	<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>
<i>Gyalosphaera sp.</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera botula</i>	<i>Navifusa acantimorpha</i>	<i>Unnamed sp. A</i>	<i>Navifusa acantimorpha</i>	<i>Obruchevella valdaica</i>	<i>Myxococcoides minor</i>	<i>Polytrichoides lineatus</i>	<i>Myxococcoides distola</i>	
<i>Herisphaera arbovelata</i>		<i>Navifusa majensis</i>		<i>Navifusa majensis</i>	<i>Oscillatorioopsis spp.</i>	<i>Ostiana microcystis</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha pileiformis</i>	<i>Myxococcoides kingii</i>	
<i>Herisphaera triangula</i>		<i>Obruchevella spp.</i>		<i>Obruchevella valdaica</i>	<i>Palaeolyngbya sp.</i>	<i>Palaeovaucheria clavata</i>	<i>Sibiriafilum tunicum</i>	<i>Myxococcoides minor</i>	
<i>Jacutianema solubila</i>		<i>Ostiana microcystis</i>		<i>Ostiana microcystis</i>	<i>Pellicularia tenera</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha insolita</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>	<i>Myxococcoides staphylidion</i>	
<i>Leiosphaeridia kulgunica</i>		<i>Pellicularia tenera</i>		<i>Palaeolyngbya catenata</i>	<i>Polytrichoides lineatus</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha pileiformis</i>	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Protosphaeridium parvulum</i>	
<i>Leiosphaeridia spp.</i>		<i>Polysphaeroides sp.</i>		<i>Pellicularia tenera</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha insolita</i>	<i>Rugosooopsis spp.</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha pileiformis</i>	
<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>		<i>Polytrichoides lineatus</i>		<i>Polysphaeroides filiformis</i>	<i>Sakta favosa</i>	<i>Segmentothallus aspergus</i>	<i>Trachytrichoides ovalis</i>	<i>Pterospermopsimorpha sp.*</i>	
<i>Microlepidopalla mira</i>		<i>Pterospermopsimorpha insolita</i>		<i>Polytrichoides lineatus</i>	<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>	<i>Simia nerjenica</i>	<i>Veteronostocale sp.</i>	<i>Siphonophycus spp.*</i>	
<i>Microlepidopalla sp.</i>		<i>Pterospermopsimorpha pileiformis</i>		<i>Pterospermopsimorpha insolita</i>	<i>Spumosina rubiginosa</i>	<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>	<i>Vidalopalla verrucata</i>	<i>Stictosphaeridium sp.</i>	
<i>Myxococcoides minor</i>		<i>Simia annulare</i>		<i>Pterospermopsimorpha pileiformis</i>	<i>Squamosphaera squamifera</i>	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>		<i>Synsphaeridium sp.*</i>	
<i>Navifusa bacillaris</i>		<i>Siphonophycus gigas</i>		<i>Rugosooopsis spp.</i>	<i>Symplassiosphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>		<i>Trachysphaeridium sp.</i>	
<i>Navifusa majensis</i>		<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>		<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>	<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Tortunema spp.</i>		<i>Trematoligotritetum emarginatum</i>	
<i>Nunatsiaquus cryptorus</i>		<i>Spiromorpha segmentata</i>		<i>Spumosina rubiginosa</i>	<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>	<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>		<i>Unnamed species A*</i>	
<i>Obruchevella valdaica</i>		<i>Spumosina rubiginosa</i>		<i>Symplassiosphaeridium spp.</i>	<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>			<i>Unnamed species B*</i>	
<i>Oscillatorioopsis spp.</i>		<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>		<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>				<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>	
<i>Ostiana microcystis</i>		<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>		<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>				<i>Veteronostocale sp.</i>	
<i>Ourasphaira giraldae</i>		<i>Tortunema spp.</i>		<i>Tortunema spp.</i>				<i>Volyniella glomerata</i>	
<i>Palaeastrum sp.</i>		<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>		<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera aimika</i>					
<i>Palaeolyngbya catenata</i>		<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera botula</i>		<i>Trachyhystrichosp haera botula</i>					
<i>Polytrichoides lineatus</i>		<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>		<i>Trachytrichoides ovalis</i>					

<i>Pterospermopsisimorpha insolita</i>		<i>Vidalopalla sp.</i>		<i>Unnamed form</i>					
<i>Pterospermopsisimorpha pileiformis</i>				<i>Valeria elongata</i>					
<i>Rugosoopsis spp.</i>				<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>					
<i>Sakta favosa</i>									
<i>Simia annulare</i>									
<i>Siphonophycus gigas</i>									
<i>Siphonophycus punctatum</i>									
<i>Squamosphaera colonialica</i>									
<i>Symplassiosphaeridium spp.</i>									
<i>Synsphaeridium spp.</i>									
<i>Syphonophycus spp.</i>									
<i>Tortunema spp.</i>									
<i>Trachyhystrichosphaera aimika</i>									
<i>Unnamed acanthomorph</i>									
<i>Unnamed filament</i>									
<i>Unnamed sphaeromorph</i>									
<i>Valeria lophostriata</i>									
<i>Vidalopalla verrucata</i>									

Supplementary Table 3. England Finder coordinates and corresponding thin sections with localities for the specimens presented in figures in this study. EF= England Finder.

Taxon	Figure	Thin section	EF coordinates	Locality
<i>Bicellum brasieri</i>	4.1-4	BC22-SH3-A	F26.4	Badenscallie
	4.5-8		H18.1	
	4.9-12	SF22-ENP	G35.3	Salmon Farm
	4.13-16		R8.2	
<i>Eohalotheca lacustrina</i>	5.1, 8, 9-11	LDR3-D	M37.1	
	5.2-7		N7.1	Lower Diabaig
	5.12, 13	LDR3-A	R6.4	
	5.14, 15		R9.4	
<i>Germinosphaera bispinosa</i>	7.1	BC22-SH3-B	S64.1	Badenscallie
	7.2	SF22-ENP	N21.1	Salmon Farm
	7.3	BC22-SH3-B	K6.3	Badenscallie
	7.4	SF22-ENP	Q19.4	Salmon Farm
<i>Leiosphaeridia</i> spp.	7.5	BC22-SH3-B	R8.4	
	7.6	BC-ACH	G21.1	
	7.7	BC22-SH3-A	X21	Badenscallie
	7.8	BC-ACH	J30.2	
	7.9	BC22-SH3-A	O23.4	
	7.10	SF22-ENP	J20	Salmon Farm
	7.11	BC22-SH3-B	L5.4	Badenscallie
	7.12		F11	
	7.13	SF22-ENP	D37.3	Salmon Farm
	7.14	RCA-1	J28.3	Road cut above Lower Diabaig
	7.15		H27.3	
	7.16	BC-ACH	N28.3	Badenscallie
	7.17	BC22-SH3-A	M22	
7.18	SF22-ENP	Q16.3	Salmon Farm	
7.19	LDR3-A	A63	Lower Diabaig	
<i>Leiosphaeridia ternata</i>	7.20		R13.2	
	7.21	LDR3-A	R12.4	Lower Diabaig
	7.22		R13.2	
<i>Minimarmilla multicateneria</i>	8.1-3		M14.3	
	8.4-5		M14.3	
	8.6		N62.3	
	8.7		J41.3	
	8.8		Q58.0	
	8.9	SF22-ENP	R47.3	Salmon Farm
	8.10		H24.4	
	8.11		M63.1	
	8.12		Q58.0	
8.13-16		L17		
<i>Pterospermopsimorpha</i> sp.	9.1-3	BC22-SH3-A	W23.2	Badenscallie
	9.4	BC22-SH3-A	E5.4	Badenscallie
<i>Synsphaeridium</i> spp.	9.5	SF22-ENP-E2	H56.3	
	9.6	SF22-ENP-E2	Q69.4	Salmon Farm

	9.7	BC22-SH3-B	S57.3-4	Badenscallie
	9.8	SF22-ENP	R18	Salmon Farm
	9.9	BC22-SH3-B	K7.2	Badenscallie
	9.10	FLO-2	Q53.4	Salmon Farm
	9.11, 12	BC22-SH3-A	Q.23	Badenscallie
	10.1	SF22-ENP-N	P39.0	
	10.2	SF22-ENP-E2	O29.0	Salmon Farm
	10.3	SF22-ENP	K18.3	
	10.4		N12.1	
	10.5		J38.2	
	10.6	RCA-1	O11	Road cut above Lower Diabaig
	10.7		S9.2	
	10.8	BC-ACH	C34	
	10.9	BC22-SH3-B	J6.3	Badenscallie
	10.10	BC-ACH	E30.1	
	10.11	SF22-ENP	N21.2	Salmon Farm
	10.12	BC22-SH3-B	Q19.4	Badenscallie
Unnamed species A	11.1-3	LDR3-D	X30.4	Lower Diabaig
	11.4, 5	BC22-SH3a	R6.1	Badenscallie
Unnamed species B	11.6, 7	SF22-ENP-Y	R51.4	Salmon Farm
	11.8	BC22-SH3-A	T2	Badenscallie

Note: The coordinates were recorded aligning the England Finder rectangle legend at the bottom left and each thin section with their label on the right, except for the samples with montaged images (see Figure 8 caption) where both rectangle legend and thin section label were oriented on the same side.

3) Supplementary Note

Supplementary Table 2 compares the Torridon taxa with other Precambrian assemblages of similar age and highlights the variety of organisms in this setting. The table expands the information in the bar chart presented in Figure 2 in the main text.

4) Supplementary References

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